

SYNTHESIS IN ACRIDINE SERIES. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF 5-METHYLACRIDINE DERIVATIVES

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2:4-Dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone on being condensed with various aromatic amines has afforded the corresponding 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivatives in good yields. These have been cyclised to the corresponding 5-methylacridine derivatives. Similarly, 2:4-dichloroacetophenone has been condensed with aniline under the conditions of Ullmann's reaction and 2-acetyl-5-chlorodiphenylamine obtained has been cyclised to 2-chloro-5-methylacridine.

Although a considerable amount of work has been done on the synthesis of 5-N-substituted acridine derivatives related to atebirin, comparatively very little work has been done on the synthesis of 5-methylacridine derivatives. The present communication deals with the synthesis of 5-methylacridine derivatives containing substituents like NO₂, Cl and -OMe.

It is well known that a 5-chloroacridine derivative condenses with various amino compounds giving rise to the corresponding 5-N-substituted acridines due to the reactivity of the chlorine atom in this position (Magidson and Grigorowsky, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 396). Similarly 5-methylacridine, due to reactivity of the methyl group in this position, undergoes condensation with various reagents, giving rise to acridine derivatives with varied substituents in 5-position. As reported by Jensen and Homberger (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 800), 5-methylacridine condenses with formaldehyde, affording 5-(β-hydroxyethyl)-acridine; the latter on oxidation yields acridine-5-carboxylic acid. Friedländer (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2840) has shown that 5-methylacridine condenses with aromatic aldehydes, particularly nitrobenzaldehyde, to yield a 5-styrylacridine derivative. Kaufmann (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1736) has reported that 5-methylacridine on condensation with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline furnishes an anil which on subsequent hydrolysis gives rise to acridine-5-aldehyde. The hydrazone of the latter has been obtained on condensation of 5-methylacridine with diazotised aniline (Koshits and Kharkharov, *Chem. Abs.*, 1945, 39, 1631).

Of the various methods available for the synthesis of 5-methylacridine, the simplest is that developed by Jensen and Rethwisch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1144). This method consists in two steps: (i) synthesis of 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivative containing the required substituents and (ii) its cyclisation to the corresponding 5-methylacridine derivative. This method has been used for the synthesis of 5-methylacridine derivatives described herein.

2-Acetyldiphenylamine is obtained by Ullmann's condensation of an *o*-aminoacetophenone derivative with halogeno-benzene or an *o*-halogeno-acetophenone with an aromatic amine (Perrina and Sargent, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 583; Jensen and Rethwisch, *loc. cit.*). The former method though proceeds smoothly affording 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivative in good yield yet it has limited application as an *o*-aminoacetophenone,

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simple or substituted, and is difficultly available ; hence the latter route consisting of the condensation of *o*-halogeno-acetophenone with an aromatic amine has been chosen for the synthesis of the required 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivatives.

Meyer (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2054) has shown that the chlorine atom, *ortho* to the acetyl group in *o*-chloroacetophenone, is not labile enough to react with an aromatic amine. But Jensen and Rethwisch (*loc. cit.*) have shown that 2-chloro-5-nitroacetophenone condenses with various aromatic amines, giving rise to the corresponding 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivatives in excellent yield ; the obvious reason for this is the increased reactivity of the chlorine atom (*ortho* to the acetyl group) due to the presence of the nitro group in its *para* position.

It has been observed here that chlorine, *ortho* to the acetyl group, is also much less reactive even in 2:4- and 2:5-dichloroacetophenones. 2:4-Dichloroacetophenone condensed with aniline yielding 5-chloro-2-acetyldiphenylamine in extremely poor yield, while the condensation of 2:5-isomer with aniline failed. However, as expected, 2:4-dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone (I), obtained on nitration of 2:4-dichloroacetophenone, condensed with aromatic amines like aniline, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-anisidine and α -naphthylamine, affording the corresponding 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivative in very good yield; the condensation of (I) with the aromatic amine having been brought about by heating the reactants in equimolecular proportions in presence of fused potassium acetate and using amyl alcohol as solvent. Use of potassium carbonate in place of the acetate and heating (I) with excess of aniline (or any aromatic amine) in presence of potassium acetate or carbonate did not prove suitable as the product obtained was highly coloured and appeared to be a mixture melting over a wide range of temperature.

The second step involving cyclisation of a 2-acetyldiphenylamine to the corresponding 5-methylacridine was effected by heating it with a solution of concentrated sulphuric acid in glacial acetic acid ; the use of concentrated sulphuric acid alone did not prove suitable due to the possibility of sulphonation of the product of the reaction. The 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivatives, obtained from (I) and various aromatic amines, were cyclised by this method and the corresponding 5-methylacridine derivatives obtained, except 7-nitro-8-chloro-5-methyl-1:2-benzacridine, were purified by extracting them with boiling solution of hydrochloric acid (10%) and reprecipitating by ammonia, since they could not be satisfactorily purified by crystallisation. Sharp *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 345) and Perrina and Sargent (*loc. cit.*) have reported that 5-methylacridines obtained on cyclisation of the required 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivative could not be satisfactorily crystallised from the usual solvents ; they have purified their products either by the above method or by subliming the product under reduced pressure. It would be interesting to note that these 5-methylacridine derivatives carrying a nitro group did not show any fluorescence in their solutions in acid or solvents like alcohol, acetone, etc.

The 2-acetyl-5-chlorodiphenylamine, obtained as a thick highly coloured semi-solid in a very low yield on Ullmann's condensation of 2:4-dichloroacetophenone with aniline, could not be isolated separately and the crude product was cyclised to obtain 2-chloro-5-methylacridine. It showed an intense green fluorescence in alcohol and acid solutions.

Further work on the study of the condensation reactions of these 5-methylacridine derivatives with various reagents, mentioned before, is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2:4-Dichloro- and 2:5-dichloro-acetophenones were obtained by Friedel-Crafts acetylation of *m*- and *p*-dichlorobenzene respectively, following the method described by Shodhan, Kshatriya and Nargund (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 373).

2-Chloro-5-methylacridine.—2:4-Dichloroacetophenone (3 g.), fused potassium carbonate (3 g.), freshly distilled aniline (10 c.c.), a trace of Cu powder and a little cuprous iodide were refluxed at 180-85° for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was steam-distilled, cooled and extracted with ether. The dark coloured liquid which remained behind on removal of ether was extracted with glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) containing H₂SO₄ (conc., 3 c.c.), and the solution was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours. The resulting solution showing an intense green fluorescence was made alkaline and the yellowish product separating was dissolved in boiling HCl solution (10%). The acid extract was cooled and made alkaline when 2-chloro-5-methylacridine separated out as a yellowish light powder. It crystallised from petrol-ether in small yellow needles, m.p. 105-106°, yield 0.10 g. It showed an intense green fluorescence in alcohol and in acid solutions. (Found: Cl, 15.8. C₁₄H₁₀NCl requires Cl, 15.6%).

The condensation of 2:5-dichloroacetophenone with aniline under the conditions of Ullmann's reaction did not succeed.

2:4-Dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone.—2:4-Dichloroacetophenone (10 g.) was added in small lots to fuming nitric acid (50 c.c., d 1.5), cooled in an ice-bath at such a rate as not to allow the temperature to rise above 5°. The reaction mixture was left in an ice bath for about 2 hours and decomposed by pouring it over crushed ice. The product separating was collected and washed with a large excess of water. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow stout needles, m.p. 62°, yield 10 g. (Found: Cl, 30.7. C₈H₅O₂NCl₂ requires Cl, 30.4%).

The *oxime* of the above ketone crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 128°. (Found: Cl, 28.7. C₈H₅O₂N₂Cl₂ requires Cl, 28.5%).

2:4-Dichloro-5-nitrobenzoic Acid.—A mixture of 2:4-dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone (2 g.) and KMnO₄ solution (150 c.c., 3%) was heated on a water-bath with constant stirring till the permanganate colour disappeared. The resulting manganese dioxide was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to half its bulk and acidified. The product separating was collected and crystallised from boiling water in yellowish small needles, m.p. 160°. (Found: Equiv., 232; Cl, 30.5. C₇H₃O₄NCl₂ requires equiv., 236; Cl, 30.1%).

2-Acetyl-4-nitro-5-chlorodiphenylamine.—The conditions described below for this condensation were established after studying it under various experimental conditions.

2:4-Dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone (10 g.), freshly distilled aniline (10 c.c.), fused potassium acetate (5 g.) and *isoamyl* alcohol (50 c.c.) were refluxed at 125-30° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was then steam-distilled to remove amyl alcohol and the residual thick liquid, sticking to the sides of the reaction flask, was washed with water and dissolved in minimum quantity of boiling alcohol and filtered. From this solution, on keeping, the product crystallised out as a heavy yellow powder, m.p. 104°, yield 13 g. (Found: Cl, 12.4. C₁₄H₁₁O₂N₂Cl requires Cl, 12.2%).

2-Chloro-3-nitro-5-methylacridine.—A solution of the preceding amine (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) containing H₂SO₄ (conc., 2.5 c.c.) was refluxed at 130°

for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was then decomposed by pouring it over crushed ice and made just alkaline. The brown product separating was collected and extracted with boiling HCl solution; a large portion of the product remained unextracted in the form of a dark sticky solid. The cooled acid extract was made alkaline when 2-chloro-3-nitro-5-methylacridine separated out as a brownish yellow powder. It was filtered, washed and dried in air. It could not be satisfactorily crystallised from usual solvents. It did not melt up to 300°, yield 2 g. (Found: Cl, 13.2. $C_{14}H_9O_2N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.0%)

4-Nitro-5-chloro-4'-methoxy-2-acetyldiphenylamine was obtained, as described above, by refluxing a mixture of 2:4-dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone (10 g.), *p*-anisidine (10 g.), fused potassium acetate (5 g.) and isoamyl alcohol (50 c.c.). It crystallised from alcohol in fine yellow granules, m. p. 124°, yield 14 g. (Found: Cl, 11.35. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.10%).

2-Chloro-3-nitro-7-methoxy-5-methylacridine, obtained on cyclisation of the above mentioned 2-acetyldiphenylamine derivative following the method described above, was purified by extraction with boiling HCl solution (10%) and reprecipitating it with alkali in light brown powder. It darkened at 195° and did not melt up to 300°. (Found: Cl, 11.97. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.70%).

4-Nitro-5:4'-dichloro-2-acetyldiphenylamine was obtained, as above, by condensing 2:4-dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone with *p*-chloroaniline. It crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow powder, m. p. 152°. (Found: Cl, 22.1. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 21.8%).

2:7-Dichloro-3-nitro-5-methylacridine was obtained on cyclisation of the above mentioned diphenylamine derivative, following the procedure described above. It was purified by extracting it with boiling dilute HCl solution. It crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture in brown powder. It did not melt up to 300°. (Found: Cl, 23.4. $C_{14}H_9O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 23.1%).

Condensation of 2:4-Dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone with α -Naphthylamine: Formation of 3-Nitro-4-chloro-6-(α -naphthyl)-aminoacetophenone.—2:4-Dichloro-5-nitroacetophenone (5 g.), α -naphthylamine (5 g.), fused potassium acetate (2.5 g.) and isoamyl alcohol (25 c.c.) were refluxed at 130° for 2 hours. The yellow product left on removal of isoamyl alcohol by steam-distillation was collected and crystallised from alcohol in yellow granules, m. p. 201-202°, yield 5 g. (Found: Cl, 10.56. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 10.40%).

7-Nitro-8-chloro-5-methyl-1:2-benzacridine.—The above mentioned diphenylamine derivative (3 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (30 c. c.) containing H_2SO_4 (conc., 3 c.c.) and the solution was heated on a water-bath for an hour. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice and made just alkaline with ammonia. The yellow solid which separated out was collected and dried. It crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture in light brown powder, m. p. 242-44° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 11.2. $C_{18}H_{11}O_2N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.0%).